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Focus Group: Developer Perception of the Benefits of MLOps for Machine Learning Applications

1.1

Introduction

This online material complements the paper "Professional Insights into Benefits and Limitations of Implementing MLOps Principles" with the detailed methodology used to conduct the two focus group discussions on the benefits and limitations of using the MLOps principles with six experienced machine learning developers and the detailed results and qualitative analyses. First, Section 1.2 focuses on the methodology, presenting the context and characterization of the participants and how the focus group was designed and conducted. Thereafter, in Section 1.3, we present the detailed focus group results on the benefits and limitations of MLOps principles. Finally, in Section 1.4, we summarize and discuss our main findings.

1.2

Methodology

To assess the MLOps principles from practitioners' point of view, we designed a focus group to promote in-depth expert discussions about the benefits and limitations of applying these principles within ML projects. Focus group is a qualitative research method based on gathering data through the conduction of group sessions, enabling extracting experiences from the participants (KONTIO; BRAGGE; LEHTOLA, 2008). A focus group session is planned for addressing in-depth discussions about a particular topic during a controlled time slot. Additionally, focus group studies have been conducted in software engineering to reveal arguments and feedback from developers (e.g. (MARTAKIS; DANEVA, 2013), (KIM; NOTKIN, 2009), (ALMEIDA et al., 2023)). Thus, we decided to use a focus group as a suitable option for understanding the developer's perception of the benefits of MLOps for supervised online Machine Learning applications.

We conducted two focus group sessions with six expert machine learning developers (three in each session) who have experience creating large-scale machine learning applications and have had contact with both MLOps and non-MLOps-based machine learning application development.

ID	Graduation Level	Years of Experience with Machine Learning	Classification of knowledge in ML	Classification of knowledge in MLOps	Job Title	Industry	Company Size
P1	Bachelor degree	3	High	Medium	ML Engineer	Retail and e-commerce	50,000+
P2	Masters Degree	4	High	Medium	Data Scientist	Oil & gas	40,000+
P3	Masters degree	5	High	Medium	Data Scientist	Oil & gas	40,000+
P4	Masters degree	3	High	Medium	ML Engineer	Oil & gas	40,000+
P5	Masters degree	4	High	Medium	ML Engineer	Oil & gas	40,000+
P6	Bachelor degree	5	Very High	High	Data Science Specialist	Finance	3,000+

Table 1.1: Focus group 1 (P1, P2, and P3) and Focus group 2 (P4, P5, and P6) participants information.

1.2.1 Context and Participant Characterization

We selected participants from three different organizations and industries to gain insights from various perspectives. We conducted two focus group sessions with six experts (P1 - P6), whose details are depicted in Table 1.1. We have collected the table data from an online Participant Characterization Form, which we sent to participants minutes before the start of the focus group session. The characterization questionnaire asked participants for their maximum academic degree, number of years working in the field of machine learning, and a rating of their knowledge of machine learning and MLOps, which could be evaluated in the following possibilities: very low, low, medium, high, very high.

It is possible to observe that all the participants have a high level of knowledge and at least 3 years of experience in developing machine-learning applications. Despite their expertise and having worked on MLOps-based projects, participants did not consider themselves highly knowledgeable on MLOps. This might be because many companies seem to be still maturing their MLOps approaches, with data scientists managing ML workflows manually to a great extent (KREUZBERGER; KÜHL; HIRSCHL, 2023).

1.2.2 Focus Group Planning and Design

We carefully designed and performed our focus group by following the guidelines proposed by (KONTIO; BRAGGE; LEHTOLA, 2008). The goal of our focus group can be described following the Goal-Question-Metric goal definition template, as follows: *Analyze the MLOps principles with the purpose of characterizing with respect to the benefits and limitations of the MLOps principles from the point of view of ML experts in the context of supervised*

online machine learning applications.

Figure 1.1 depicts the steps adopted throughout the focus group. We organized these steps in three major phases: **(1)** Preparation for the focus group session; **(2)** Conducting the focus group sessions; and **(3)** Analyzing the data and reporting the results. We describe each phase and step hereafter.

Figure 1.1: Focus Group Overview.

Phase 1: Preparation for the focus group session - This phase consists of the collection of preliminary resources for supporting the execution of the focus group session. For this purpose, we follow two steps.

Step 1 - Recruit developers consisted of recruiting developers with experience in machine learning and MLOps to engage in discussions. We contacted developers from three different organizations and industries to participate in our study. We obtained the acceptance of six experts via a Consent Form in which we explained our research goals and that the information provided by each participant will be treated confidentially and used for study purposes only.

Step 2 - Characterize participants aimed to collect basic information to characterize the participants via the Participant Characterization Form. Our major goal was profiling each developer so we could better interpret our study results. We collected data on the education level, years of experience with machine learning development, and a rating of their knowledge of machine learning and MLOps development (Table 1.1).

Phase 2: Conducting the focus group sessions - This phase consists of collecting data regarding the developer’s perception of the benefits and limitations of using the MLOps principles for supervised online machine learning applications. To discuss the benefits and limitations of MLOps, we derived statements regarding commonly used ML-based software delivery metrics (deployment frequency, lead-time for change, and mean time to restore) (VISENGERIYEVA et al., 2023), and asked participants to discuss the effects of using MLOps on these metrics. As these metrics mainly concern automation (including deployment, reproducibility, and testing aspects), we added two additional statements to allow discussions regarding the monitoring and versioning principles. Finally, we added a generic statement on using MLOps principles to gather any additional insights that the experts would like to provide.

We used an online environment to promote discussions on the benefits and limitations of MLOps principles for machine learning applications. Figure 1.2 illustrates the virtual template that we designed using the MIRO online tool. In practice, by using this tool, we were able to build an interactive mural to facilitate the conduction of the focus group sessions.

Figure 1.2: Focus Group Template.

Our template is divided into 5 columns that seek to understand whether,

for each line containing a statement, the participants, through virtual post-its: strongly agree, partially agree, partially disagree, strongly disagree, or have no opinion over it. Each statement is discussed in isolation, and we defined the dynamics of the focus group session in three steps as follows:

Step 1 - Introduce the statement aimed at introducing each statement. For this purpose, the moderator of the session read this information out loud. Next, in **Step 2 - Add comments**, we asked each participant to add one or more *post-it* for each comment it has over the statement, as in part. Finally, in **Step 3 - Discuss comments**, we asked the participants to explain their comments (and why they agreed or disagreed with the statement) and discussed them within the group. Each comment should be documented as a comment on the post-it as shown in Figure 1.3. The comment was just a brief summary of the reason they selected a column, and we constantly asked participants to share knowledge and experiences surrounding the statement to enrich the discussions and understanding. Additionally, whenever the moderator felt that a comment was poorly written, he asked the participants to provide further considerations.

We emphasize that the focus group session was conducted online via a Zoom Meeting. Additionally, we kept video and audio records of the session to support the data analysis. Both sessions were conducted in August 2023.

Figure 1.3: Focus Group Template Steps.

Phase 3: Analyzing the data and reporting the results - in this phase, we analyzed the comments for each statement, also referring to the transcribed audio discussion records to better understand what developers meant with each note. The audio records of the Zoom recording were transcribed using a popular speech-to-text transcription model developed at PUC-Rio's Informatics Department (GROSMAN, 2021). We report the results for each statement in the following section.

1.3 Results

We asked the participants to choose and justify whether they agreed or disagreed with the statements reported under the context of the benefits and limitations of using the principles of MLOps for supervised online machine learning applications. We have collected these comments through post-it notes added by the participants in the session's virtual mural (as illustrated in Figure 1.3).

In order to analyze these comments, we first watched the video and automatically transcribed its audio into plain text. Thereafter, we analyzed all post-it comments written by the participants and associated transcription quotes. In the following subsections, we summarize the comments that emerged for each statement.

1.3.1 **Deployment frequency: Using MLOps principles helps me to have more frequent deploys and, consequently, more constant value deliveries**

This statement focuses on the deployment frequency metric that is strongly related to the automation principle for MLOps. We expected the participants to discuss how MLOps could help the deployment process and generate more valuable and constant deliveries. Four reported to strongly agree, one participant reported to strongly agree and partially agree, and one participant reported to partially agree. We detail each comment as follows, grouped by strongly agree and partially agree ones.

Strongly agree: One of the main topics discussed was that the use of these principles does tend to be favorable for deliveries with more value, but this is also much related to the real needs of the product.

"If you have a "far away" deadline, with broken and well-defined deliveries, i.e. a broad roadmap, the impact of MLOps ends up being huge. If the first version of the product delivers what you need in practice, the first delivery is already what you need, and MLOps ends up having a low impact." - P6

Despite being in different groups, participants P6 and P5 (Focus Group 2), and P3 and P1 (Focus Group 1), stressed the same point. For both groups, the positive impact of the deployment frequency principles is closely related to the product and application context. As P6 stated, if a product doesn't have a high deployment frequency, it is not worth the effort to prepare a

well-structured pipeline following the MLOps principles, which require development and preparation time, instead of using that effort on other fronts.

"Creating a well-defined structure can be very complicated. Creating a deployment pipeline can be very good, but it depends on how it's structured. Having an already in-progress pipeline first can help. If a pipeline is robust with good practices, the value ends up being very high, but getting there is complicated." - P3

In P3's opinion, which was agreed with by participants P1 and P2, the maturity of the deployment pipeline process needs to be at a high-automated level for there to be a significant impact. I.e., they believe that the principle can have an effect on the number of deploys and thus generate more value with constant deliveries; however, this is only true with a roadmap containing automation elements such as pipelines for continuous integration, continuous delivery, model continuous delivery, and monitoring.

Figure 1.4: P3-P1-P2 Strongly Agree post-its to the sentence "Deployment frequency: Using good MLOps practices helps me to have more frequent deploys and, consequently, more constant value deliveries."

Figure 1.5: P6-P5 Strongly Agree post-its to the sentence "Deployment frequency: Using good MLOps practices helps me to have more frequent deploys and, consequently, more constant value deliveries."

Partially agree: P4 and P5 both mentioned that a manual or poorly structured deployment process tends to generate stress and possibly human error and that, in their experience, they have seen that in these scenarios the development team tends to be afraid to carry out deploys and, consequently, tends to reduce the number of deploys made in order to avoid going through the "traumatic" process. P4 and P5 agreed that the ease of deployment creates more opportunities for development to focus on higher-quality deliveries and other points for improvement.

Figure 1.6: P4-P5 Partially Agree post-its to the sentence "Deployment frequency: Using good MLOps practices helps me to have more frequent deploys and, consequently, more constant value deliveries."

Overall, with respect to deployment frequency, we conclude that participants mainly agree that MLOps principles help to generate more frequent deploys and more value deliveries. On the other hand, they also mentioned that if a product doesn't require a high deployment frequency, it might not be worth the effort to prepare a well-structured pipeline following the MLOps principles, which require development and preparation time, instead of using that effort on other fronts.

1.3.2

Lead time for changes: Using the good practices of MLOps helps me to reduce the time for delivery and deployment, counting from the moment the code is merged

In this statement, we approached another important metric related to the automation principle. The statement intended to understand the experts' experiences on how the automation principle can affect the lead time for changes, i.e. do the MLOps principles help the developers to have code merged faster into a production environment? Four participants reported strongly agree, one participant reported both strongly agree and partially agree, and one reported partially agree. We separate each comment as follows, grouped by strongly agree and partially agree ones.

Strongly Agree: Participant P3 assesses this as one of the main impacts of using MLOPs: the more mature your pipeline, the greater the reduction in lead time. The cost of a manual deployment, of misconfiguring non-automated resources, is high. In addition, reducing the need for manual processes also reduces maintenance time due to problems generated during manual deployments. P4 agreed that the reduction in manual processes tends to reduce the time for changes was the main factor, given that we are analyzing from the moment the commit is merged.

P1 agrees and raises the counterpoint seen in the previous statement that this process of pipeline maturity is time-consuming and, consequently, requires effort and time. So it's important to always weigh up when it's time to automate the process so that it's really worth being in automated mode and no longer manual.

Again, both groups address the same points as P3 (Focus Group 1) raised the same discussion as P6 and P4 (Focus Group 2) about reducing errors generated by manual processes that, consequently, require human intervention.

"Good practices such as versioning and automation help corrections as a matter of urgency. When you incorporate good practices, you reduce manual steps and of course, human errors, standardizing changes and speeding up delivery." - P6

Figure 1.7: P3-P1 Strongly Agree post-its to the sentence "Lead time for changes: Using the good practices of MLOps helps me to reduce the time for delivery and deployment, counting from the moment the code is merged."

Figure 1.8: P5-P4-P6 Strongly Agree post-its to the sentence "Lead time for changes: Using the good practices of MLOps helps me to reduce the time for delivery and deployment, counting from the moment the code is merged."

Partially Agree: P2 believes that this sentence is "partially correct." In their opinion, sometimes delivering a product with value in a more agile way, with less automation and without following MLOps principles, especially in the so-called initial versions (or v0, i.e. version zero), can be more favorable to the company business. P2 states that it's not necessarily every new product will reach the level of needing to have a well-optimized pipeline and thus a low lead time to change. P1 enforces the argument, again emphasizing how important it is to understand the need for a well-automated deployment structure consistent with your project's real needs, such as its scalability.

Figure 1.9: P2-P1 Partially Agree post-its to the sentence "Lead time for changes: Using the good practices of MLOps helps me to reduce the time for delivery and deployment, counting from the moment the code is merged."

Hence, for lead time to production, it is possible to observe an overall agreement on the reduction of the time for delivery and deployment. Indeed, MLOps principles such as versioning and automation are perceived as helping corrections as a matter of urgency. When you incorporate MLOps principles, you reduce manual steps and human errors, standardizing changes and speeding up delivery.

1.3.3

Mean Time to Restore: From the moment an incident happens and there is a need for rollback, I can go back to my model in the previous version easily, without using continuous deployment practices

This statement was set to understand how the MLOps principles might influence moments of urgency, such as a bug in a production environment. It addresses the mean time to restore metric, i.e. the time it takes an application to recover, usually through a rollback, to a functional state from a non-functional state. This process, which commonly involves a new deployment, tends to be done at moments of tension and stress, as a problem in production can cause damage to the application model, ruining data, as well as possible financial damage to the company, depending on what the application is used to. By bringing up this discussion, our goal is to understand whether, in the experience of our participants, this process done manually and without reproducibility principles and continuous deployment practices is seen as viable.

In this statement, three participants reported partially disagreeing, and three reported strongly disagreeing. Following, we detail each comment grouped by partially disagree and strongly disagree.

Partially disagree: Comments from participants P1, P5, and P6 were on the subject of the maturity of two components: the deployment pipeline and the application as a whole. For P5 and P6, the complexity of their dataset, model, and code influences their ability to do a rollback if necessary. P5 shared that, in a recent experience, it was possible to maintain a description and store each model and dataset created by the development team manually, but as the application gained scope and naturally grew, it became impossible to maintain this manually.

Participant P6 adds that this non-automated versioning, i.e. without following the MLOps principles, can be done, but it is common for one of the three scopes that need to be versioned (data, code, and model) not to be stored in a structured way, making the rollback process difficult. In other words, it is important to have a mature pipeline containing continuous delivery so that it is possible to perform a rollback, but it would not be impossible, in the early stages of a machine learning application, to do this versioning and storage manually, and performing a manual rollback.

"At one of the projects I worked on, I used a platform that helps automate my machine learning application. Even though we paid for this platform to help with the process, it still required a specific configuration from the internal development team to structure the versioning. When we needed to perform a rollback using what was built through the platform, we discovered that there was an error in the way we structured the versioning, and even with a platform helping with the continuous deployment process, we were unable to execute the rollback easily." - P1

Through this practical example from participant P1, in their opinion, as the application grows, versioning needs to be well structured so that rollbacks can be carried out quickly and easily.

Figure 1.10: P1 Partially Disagree post-its to the sentence "Mean Time to Restore: From the moment an incident happens and there is a need for rollback, I can go back to my model in the previous version easily, without using continuous deployment practices."

Figure 1.11: P5-P6 Partially Disagree post-its to the sentence "Mean Time to Restore: From the moment an incident happens and there is a need for rollback, I can go back to my model in the previous version easily, without using continuous deployment practices."

Strongly disagree: In P2 and P3's experience, structuring data correctly is an essential part of a supervised online machine learning application. For P2, returning to previous versions without versioning can be impossible. They state that there's no going back if you don't have traceability of the changed data. P3 points out that an application without the principle of versioning as part of the good practices of continuous deployment tends not to be "reliable."

"Without these [continuous deployment practices], it seems that the application will never be reliable. Without good practices and continuous deployment, we lose the reduction of several steps, such as testing, which avoids the causes of incidents and new incidents when restoring an already ongoing incident, which can happen without good practices. We don't have security." - P3

Participant P4 raised a different point of view: the human side of having a problem in production. According to the participant, there is an impact on people under pressure during a crisis, such as a bug in production, which increases the likelihood of human error. Therefore, an automated continuous deployment process is one of the main benefits of following the MLOps principles. In P4's opinion, crisis recovery and decision-making tend to be "easier" when there is an automated process that doesn't need to be taken into account during the crisis.

Figure 1.12: P3-P2 Strongly Disagree post-its to the sentence "Mean Time to Restore: From the moment an incident happens and there is a need for rollback, I can go back to my model in the previous version easily, without using continuous deployment practices."

Figure 1.13: P4 Strongly Disagree post-its to the sentence "Mean Time to Restore: From the moment an incident happens and there is a need for rollback, I can go back to my model in the previous version easily, without using continuous deployment practices."

Therefore, with respect to mean time to restore, it is understandable that participants mainly agree that maintaining code, datasets, and model versioned and stored manually in the early stages of a machine learning application will make the processes feasible. However, by providing a structured pipeline following the automation and versioning principles, a machine learning application tends to make the reproducibility and rollback process easier and more successful, avoiding error-prone manual steps.

1.3.4

Monitoring: Setting up alarms and monitoring is made easy without the use of MLOps

This statement's goal is to evaluate the use of MLOps to ensure monitoring by reflecting on whether, in the experience of the experts, it was possible to achieve monitoring and alarmist with quality in their projects without relying on the MLOps principles.

For this statement, one participant reported partially agreeing, two partially disagreeing, one strongly disagreeing, and two reported not having a formed opinion on the topic. The opinions on this statement were very diverse, as well as being the topic with the highest number of participants reporting that they had no opinion on the subject. Following are the opinions provided

by the participants.

Partially agree: P6 was the only participant who reported partially agreeing that even without the use of MLOPs, it is possible to create alarms and monitoring in a smooth manner. In the participant's opinion, it is possible, but with a greater amount of effort. P6 pointed out that in their experience in different projects and companies, the monitoring part took a back seat during the prioritization of the project tasks.

In addition, P6 commented that the implementation of monitoring and alarmists arises from necessity when the first "pain" of not having monitoring occurs. In these cases, the negative experience generated by the lack of monitoring creates an urgency to develop it and, consequently, in the need to have something implemented quickly, the practices presented in the MLOps principle were left behind. We then asked: "Even without following the principles, was what was generated considered sufficient?" - the answer was positive, which we believe justifies their partially favorable opinion of the statement.

Figure 1.14: P6 Partially Agree post-its to the sentence "Monitoring: Setting up alarms and monitoring is made easy without the use of MLOps."

Partially disagree: Participants P5 and P4 reported partially disagreeing with the statement. In their opinion, the possibility of creating alarms and monitoring, in general, depends little on the implementation process, but they believe that the MLOps principles practiced in areas other than monitoring specifically can facilitate the development of alarms and monitors.

"Even in projects I've worked on that didn't use MLOPs, we already had some alarms that worked well." - P5

Figure 1.15: P4-P5 Partially Disagree post-its to the sentence "Monitoring: Setting up alarms and monitoring is made easy without the use of MLOps."

Strongly disagree: P3 reported strongly disagreeing that setting up alarms and monitoring is made easy without the use of MLOps. In their opinion, although it is possible to set up monitoring without MLOps, it enhances speed, agility, automation, and integration for more effective and consistent monitoring practices. The participant stated that monitoring following the MLOps principles generates alerts proactively, i.e. following the principles and good practices dictated by MLOps will naturally generate a scenario prone to creating monitoring and alarms more smoothly. The participant states:

"Creating alarms and monitoring without using MLOps is like having a hammer and missing the other tools needed to build a house." - P3

Figure 1.16: P3 Strongly Disagree post-its to the sentence "Monitoring: Setting up alarms and monitoring is made easy without the use of MLOps."

No opinion: Participant P2 stated that they didn't have enough experience on the subject to feel comfortable giving an opinion.

However, participant P1 stated that his decision to place himself without an opinion was due to positive and negative experiences with using and not using the MLOps principles. Like other participants, their belief is that it is possible to create monitoring and alarms without using the principles, but that if the MLOps principles are used, implementation tends to have better quality and is easier. P1 adds that there are trade-offs on both sides depending on terms like the timing of the project, the number of people available, and, consequently, the effort available to implement good practices and MLOps principles.

In their opinion, the area of monitoring and alarming is not considered relevant and talked about in machine learning circles, and although they have seen a greater focus on the subject recently, the topic is generally raised by people who have knowledge of software engineering beyond the application in machine learning projects.

P1 also points out that monitoring doesn't need to be extensive and complex at the outset; identifying an anomaly and sending a warning by email or a communication platform can be considered that an application is being monitored and alarmed, even if it may be inefficient sometimes. P1 points out that the important thing is for this culture of monitoring and alarmism to be discussed "more and more" among machine learning developers so that,

through these discussions, the maturity of the machine learning's monitoring culture can be improved.

Figure 1.17: P1-P2 No Opinion post-its to the sentence "Monitoring: Setting up alarms and monitoring is made easy without the use of MLOps."

Overall, with respect to monitoring, we can observe that, even though the participants' opinions about the statement were diverse, a common aspect was that monitoring is usually left behind from the application scope in the early stages. We can also conclude that it is possible to build monitoring without following the MLOps principles; however, implementing the MLOps principles will facilitate and come into great hands when developing alarms and monitors.

1.3.5

Versioning: In my projects that did not use MLOps principles, I was able to migrate between the deploys made from my service

Through this statement, our goal is to understand from the experts' opinions whether they consider it feasible to carry out common actions such as rollback and model version exchange (reproducibility) in projects that did not use the MLOps principles in their implementation.

Two participants reported partially disagreeing, and four reported strongly disagreeing with the statement. Following, we present the arguments from the participants over why they partially or strongly disagree with the statement.

Partially disagree: As previously reported, the two participants who reported partially disagreeing with the sentence gave examples of projects they had worked on and were able to maintain without versioning. In all cases, however, it was only possible to maintain the project without versioning principles being implemented in the early stages of the project. P5 stated that not following the MLOps principles implies the need to maintain a very organized manual process so that no time is wasted in times of urgency, such as when performing rollbacks during a bug in the production environment.

Participant P3 stated that they believe it is possible to implement initial forms of versioning without following the MLOps principles, but through good practices, it will be possible to achieve a more systematic and automated approach to version management and migrations.

Figure 1.18: P3 Partially Disagree post-its to the sentence "Versioning: In my projects that did not use MLOps principles, I was able to migrate between the deploys made from my service."

Figure 1.19: P5 Partially Disagree post-its to the sentence "Versioning: In my projects that did not use MLOps principles, I was able to migrate between the deploys made from my service."

Strongly disagree: A common point in almost all the comments from participants who strongly disagree is that the versioning principle is essential for achieving quality. P4 commented on their not believing in the possibility of a team developing an application to an acceptable level of quality without automated version control. The participant also pointed out their very negative experiences in projects that didn't prioritize developing a versioning process at first, and the consequences were negative as the project progressed.

For P1 and P2, the trade-offs of not implementing good versioning MLOps practices are "indisputable." P2 states that the effort spent in the short term is rewarded exponentially over a short period of time through the common need to migrate between versioning code, data, and models.

"You gain little by not having and lose a lot by not having." - P1

Figure 1.20: P1-P2 Strongly Disagree post-its to the sentence "Versioning: In my projects that did not use MLOps principles, I was able to migrate between the deploys made from my service."

Figure 1.21: P6-P4 Strongly Disagree post-its to the sentence "Versioning: In my projects that did not use MLOps principles, I was able to migrate between the deploys made from my service."

Thereupon, for versioning, it is possible to observe an overall disagreement with the feasibility of running a complex production-ready machine learning application without the MLOps principles. Aside from early-stage machine learning applications, versioning plays an important part in making possible

reproducibility by enabling previous datasets and models to be identified and facilitating the application to perform rollback to previously trained models and labeled datasets.

1.3.6

General MLOps principles: I understand that the principles of MLOps help me to deliver faster and more concisely, generating greater value for my application

This statement was added as a generic statement on using MLOps principles to gather any additional insights that the experts would like to provide. It brings the focus to the use of MLOps principles in delivering complex and valuable machine learning applications, suggesting the use of MLOps principles as a tool that helps developers to deliver faster and more concisely.

Hence, the discussion of this last topic was almost a summary of all the points covered in the previous statements. Indeed, we had five participants who reported strongly agreeing and one who reported partially disagreeing. Below, we detail each of these comments grouped by strong agreement and partial disagreement.

Strongly agree: Understandably, this was the statement with the least heterogeneous range of responses between the two groups of participants. However, the comments by which the participants justified their decision were diverse.

For P2, the principles generate faster and more valuable deliveries, especially in the automation part of the life cycle.

Participant P1 states that development should avoid going overboard with the use of tools that don't make sense for the project. The participant comments that the important thing, in their opinion, is that there is clear planning about what needs to be delivered as a product from the start of the project and that this planning should take into account "the good practices implementation", as part of the basic implementation of a machine learning application.

In their experience, the problem usually lies when the project planning isn't done precisely and, moreover, is done by company teams that don't take into account the entire scope of a project with implementation quality.

"You need to know your reality and your problem in order to know how to act on it. MLOps is not a job, it's a culture, and if you want to use MLOps you have to face it as a culture and bring people into your team who follow

and believe in that culture to get there." - P1

Participant P3 adds that creating an environment that uses the MLOps principles is a constant duty of self-awareness, which is independent of the maturity of the company or project in which it is being developed.

"The delivery of valuable deployments is continuous, the machine learning applications can have multiple functionalities and each delivery generates more value. To be fast is to be consistent with the schedule, and the principles of MLOps favor this delivery in the schedule if it is well suited. The biggest problem is how to make this schedule fit, having to align it with the product team. We lack the maturity to be able to bring these principles into the schedule." - P3

Participant P6 said that their experience with "the two sides of the same coin" highlights that the project creation process is closely linked to the need to follow and use these principles. For the participant, the creation process should make the project's intent clear and this should be enough to decide whether or not to implement the MLOps principles. A project with a short scope, with low maintenance needs, is not usually worth the effort of having a well-planned and thought-out structure using the MLOps principles; on the other hand, a large-scale, complex project, mostly online, has the implementation of the MLOps principles as an almost essential basis for the success of the project, with a view to quality of the project in the long term.

Figure 1.22: P1-P3-P2 Strongly Agree post-its to the sentence "General: I understand that the principles of MLOps help me to deliver faster and more concisely, generating greater value for my application."

Figure 1.23: P5-P6 Strongly Agree post-its to the sentence "General: I understand that the principles of MLOps help me to deliver faster and more concisely, generating greater value for my application."

Partially disagree: Participant P4 was the only one who declared not to strongly agree with the statement. Despite the surprising opposite of the majority, the explanation of why the participant chose to disagree with the statement was considered fair and reasonable by the other participants.

The participant explains that although they have knowledge about MLOps and their benefits, this knowledge was not obtained in their work environment but through private interest and study. P4 points out that the problem, in their opinion, is not the characteristics of MLOps but rather both the academia and industry environments, which do not have MLOps as part of their culture. They believe that today there is a need to create a culture of knowledge and use of MLOps, especially in academia, and that this maturing will increasingly influence the need to use these principles, i.e. as few companies use these principles today, their benefits are not seen competitively.

Figure 1.24: P4 Partially Disagree post-its to the sentence "General: I understand that the principles of MLOps help me to deliver faster and more concisely, generating greater value for my application."

While there is mainly an agreement, the partially disagreeing comment is similar to what we observed in the previous statements: the use of MLOps principles is closely related to the need and capacity to implement them. Although the benefits are understandable compared to mature projects, implementing the MLOps principles could imply changing and delaying the planned roadmap, which is usually focused on delivering usable results. The culture of using MLOps as a basic part of developing complex software with quality is not yet so disseminated.

1.4 Discussion

In Section 1.3, we collected from the participants multiple insights that we believe assess the benefits and limitations of using MLOps for supervised online machine learning applications. Indeed, from the enriching discussions, we summarize some of the highlights that were brought up:

- The development team should consider the product scope and roadmap before implementing some MLOps principles. If a product doesn't have a high deployment frequency, it might not be worth the effort to prepare a well-structured pipeline following the MLOps principles, which require development and preparation time.
- MLOps practices can help corrections as a matter of urgency. When the development team incorporates MLOps principles such as automation and versioning, it might reduce manual steps and human errors, standardizing changes and speeding up delivery.
- Performing an application version change or a rollback is possible without implementing MLOps principles such as an automated deployment pipeline and versioning for an early-stage application. Even so, it is common for an early-stage non-automated pipeline to fail or make the rollback process longer.
- Monitoring usually takes a back seat during the prioritization of the project tasks. That might explain the multiple arguments and viewpoints the two groups discussed over the topic. It was stated that it's possible to create alarms and monitoring, even if they are not too elaborate. Even so, having MLOps principles implemented will facilitate and come into great hands when developing alarms and monitors.
- Keeping the implementation at a good quality level without versioning is feasible in the early stages of the implementation. Afterward, it usually becomes complicated to maintain an application that does not have versioning of code, model, and/or data.
- The culture of creating good quality software by following good engineering practices, including the MLOps principles, is still not so well spread over the academia and industry machine learning companies. Creating an environment that uses the MLOps principles is a constant duty of self-awareness and should be aligned with the project requirements. It may be facilitated by the maturity of the company or project in which it is being developed.

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